

THERMOPHYSICAL AND TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH BORON CARBIDE PARTICULATES

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1 Introduction

Particulate reinforcements in conjunction with traditional two-phase fiber composites provide unique behaviors as a hybrid composite system. The particulate material influences the thermo physical characteristics of these material systems and often leads to changes in the performance and failure characteristics. The present paper focuses on epoxy - fiberglass composites hybridized with Boron carbide (B_4C) nanoparticles with a potential for radiation shielding in interplanetary environment. EPON 862 resin modified with the addition of small percentages of B_4C nanoparticles was infiltrated in sequentially laid stacks of fiber glass preform via Heated Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (HVARTM). Addition of B_4C nanoparticles influenced the curing of EPON 862 resin. These nanoparticles also had an impact on the mechanical properties of the resulting hybrid composite.

Deep space radiations pose a major threat to the astronauts and their space craft during the long duration space exploration expeditions [1]. The radiation that are of main concern are the galactic cosmic radiation (GCR), and the short lived secondary neutron radiations that are generated as a result of fragmentation that proceeds when GCR strikes target nuclei in a spacecraft. GCR primarily consists of hydrogen and helium. Shielding from GCR is effectively accomplished via Coulombic interaction of GCR nucleus and electrons with nuclei of the target material.

Energy loss during the interaction of GCR and shielding material increases with the charge to mass ratio of the shielding material. Hydrogen with no neutron in its nucleus has the highest charge to mass

ratio and is the element which is most effective shield against GCR. Polymers because of their high hydrogen content serve as radiation shield materials as shown in Table 1 [2-4]. Ideal shielding material is the one which will offer protection from GCR and impede the secondary neutron radiations that result from the fragmentation process. Neutron that result from fragmentation, do not respond to the Coulombic interaction that shield against GCR. To prevent the deleterious effects of secondary neutrons, what is required is the target such as Boron, Gadolinium or Tungsten with relatively large neutron cross-sections [5]. Composites of ethylene-propylene diene rubber, and low density polyethylene made with different concentrations of boron carbide powder, when investigated for their gamma and slow neutron radiation shielding properties were shown to reduce the flux of incident neutron by about 85 % [6]. Similarly, it has also been successfully demonstrated that among the different boron-rich additives, nanoparticles of boron carbide make good multifunctional composites if they are paired with polymers having high levels of hydrogen, such as polyethylene [7].

In general, straight chain aliphatic polymers due to their higher hydrogen content would be more suited as deep space radiation shield materials [8-10]. However, this class of polymers lack thermal and structural stability that is required for long duration space exploration expeditions. Aromatic polymers, which include epoxies, have higher strength and are thermally more stable than aliphatic polymers. Also, epoxies can withstand higher radiation doses before they can breakdown [11]. By using aromatic polymers such as epoxies, it is possible to integrate radiation shield material into the structural

components of the spacecraft. Elements with high neutron capture radii in the form of boron carbide in conjunction with aromatic polymer can also provide protection against secondary neutrons generated as a result of fragmentation.

2 Experimental Studies

2.1 Materials and Processing

The fiber reinforcement used is 10K plain bi-directional woven S2 fiberglass fabric supplied by BGF industries. B₄C used in the present study is manufactured by Electro Abrasives. The particle size and size distribution of the as-received boron carbide powder was determined using Zetatrac nanotechnology particle size and charge measuring equipment marketed by Microtrac®. The particle size distribution was determined using Zetatrac particle size analyzer. The B₄C particle size varied from 0.1 to 1.0 μm with the mean particle size being 0.35 micron.

Epon 862 (a bis-phenol F epoxy) and “EpiCure” curing agent used in the present study were purchased from Miller-Stephenson Chemical Company, Inc.

Epoxy/fiberglass composites with and without B₄C nanoparticulates were fabricated via heated vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (HVARTM) [12]. After laying ten layers of glass fiber mat one over the other, the entire mold was sealed with high temperature sealant and vacuum bag. Use of heat during HVARTM ensures thorough infusion of resin into the fabric. Epoxy/fiberglass composite was hybridized with B₄C nanoparticulates by modifying the resin during HVARTM. The resin modification involved dispersion of B₄C nanoparticulates in the resin. Dispersion of B₄C nanoparticulates in the resin was achieved by sonication for 15 minutes at 60% of power amplitude and was pulsed on for about one minute and off for 10 seconds to prevent heat build-up in the system.

During HVARTM, attempts to infiltrate glass fiber mats with resin containing 10 and 5 weight percent of B₄C resulted in incomplete percolation of resin in the fiber mat. As a result, it was decided to apply resin containing 5 wt. % B₄C using a brush on either side of the fiber glass mat before stacking them one over the other during HVARTM. The vacuum and compression in HVARTM was utilized for the resin infusion and compaction of the fabric layers.

2.2 Characterization

2.2.1 Thermo-Physical Characterization (Differential Scanning Calorimetry)

DSC 6000 from Perkin Elmer was used to obtain temperature scan for the resin hardener mixture with and without 5 wt. % B₄C. Temperature scans were obtained by maintaining the resin hardener mixture at 25 °C for one minute followed by heating the mixture using a specified heating rate. DSC was also used to monitor the glass transition temperature of the neat resin and hybrid composites. The storage modulus and Tan-δ of neat resin and hybrid composites were evaluated using DMA8000 supplied by Perkin Elmer. The specimens were heated from room temperature to 200 °C with a heating rate of 2 °C/min. Double cantilever mode was used to test the specimens at the frequency of 1 Hz.

2.2.2 Mechanical Characterization

Tensile test specimens were fabricated according to ASTM D3039 test specimen specifications. Tensile testing was conducted according to the ASTM D3039M test standard using 133 KN Instron machine. These tests were conducted using a crosshead speed of 5.08 mm/min (0.2 inch/min).

The fracture surface of Epoxy/fiberglass composites with and without B₄C nanoparticulates were analyzed using Orion plus helium ion microscope.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Thermo-Physical Characterization:

Activation Energy of Curing for EPON 862 Resin

Activation energy associated with the curing of EPON 862 resin was calculated using Flynn-Wall method. Following is the Flynn-Wall expression,

$$\log \beta = \log \frac{AE_a}{g(\alpha)R} - 2.315 - \frac{0.457E_a}{RT} \quad (1)$$

β is the heating rate in degrees/minute

E_a is the activation energy in kJ/mole

“T” is the peak temperature in Deg. Kelvin

g(α) is the integral function of conversion, α

R is the gas constant

Isothermal differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) method was used to determine the activation energy associated with the curing of EPON 862 resin. The

exothermic peaks in the DSC curves shown in Figure 1 correspond to the peak temperature required for the curing of the epoxy resin. The test sample for the DSC experiments was drawn from the pool of resin hardener mixture. The pool of resin hardener mixture was produced by thoroughly mixing 100 grams of EPON 862 resin with 26 grams of Epicure curing agent.

From the peak temperature value reported in Figure 1 for each heating rate, activation energy was determined using Flynn Wall expression. Table 2 shows the parameters associated with the EPON 862 hardener mixture. Non-isoconversional curve for EPON 862-Epicure hardener mixture from Flynn Wall expression was used to compute the activation energy associated with the curing process. Similar exercise was repeated to determine activation energy associated with the curing process for EPON 862 resin in presence of 5 weight percent B_4C . The exothermic peaks in the DSC curves shown in Figure 2 correspond to the peak temperature required for the curing of the epoxy resin in presence of 5 weight percentage B_4C . 5 weight percentage B_4C was chosen because higher B_4C content in the resin adversely affected the flow of the resin during HVARTM.

From the peak temperature value reported in Figure 2 for each heating rate, activation energy involved with the curing of EPON 862 resin in presence of 5 weight percent B_4C was determined and is reported in Table 3. In presence of 5 weight percent B_4C , activation energy required for the curing of the EPON 862 resin was found to be comparable to that of activation energy required for the curing of neat resin. Elsewhere, addition of Montmorillonite has been shown to have catalytic effect on curing kinetics of polybenoxazine /clay hybrid composite [13].

3.2 Tensile Characterization

The tensile deformation behavior and associated stress strain curves of EPON 862 /Fiber glass composite before and after hybridization with 5 weight percent B_4C nanoparticulates were obtained. The stress-strain data indicates that EPON 862 - Fiber glass composite behaves like a perfectly elastic material. EPON 862 - Fiber glass composites tested in this work have an average strength of 161 MPa. As seen in Table 4, with the insertion of 5 weight

percent B_4C nanoparticulates there is a decrease in the average strain to failure and tensile strength of the composite. The elastic modulus values from the present work are comparable and consistent with the storage modulus values measured using dynamic mechanical analyzer.

Figure 3 presents the fractograph of EPON 862 - Fiber glass composite specimen after tensile characterization. Fracture surface of EPON 862 - Fiber glass composite by and large appeared to be flat with isolated evidence of energy dissipating mechanism such as fiber pullout. Feather like features in the matrix region seen in Figure 3 is an indication that in case of EPON 862 - Fiber glass composite, EPON 862 matrix behaves in a ductile manner [14]. As seen in Figure 4, when EPON 862 - fiberglass composite was hybridized with B_4C nanoparticulates, the failure mechanism of the resultant hybrid composite appeared to be predominantly fiber pullout.

Higher magnification of the fractured surfaces clearly indicates that the weak fiber matrix interface in EPON 862 - fiberglass composite hybridized with B_4C is due to the inability of the modified EPON 862 matrix, to flow around all the fibers during fabrication of hybrid composite via heated vacuum assisted resin transfer molding. It is also evident from higher resolution fractography that while the fibers in the periphery of the tow constituting the woven mat are coated with B_4C particles, the wave front of the modified resin that reach the fibers in the interior of the tow is devoid of these particles. By the time the EPON 862 resin modified with dispersion of B_4C nanoparticulates approaches the surface of the fibers in the interior of the tow constituting the woven fiber preform; it solidifies and partially covers the fiber surface. This is likely to create a weak fiber matrix interface.

3.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

The storage modulus measured using dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) is closely related to the load bearing capability of the composite. Figure 5 shows the variation of storage modulus with temperature in case of EPON 862 resin and EPON 862-fiber glass composite with and without B_4C nanoparticulates. In case of EPON 862 resin, storage modulus is not significantly altered with addition of 5 weight percent B_4C nanoparticulates. However, 5

weight percent B₄C nanoparticulate addition does seem to bring about appreciable change in the storage modulus of EPON 862 - fiber glass composite. Similar conclusion can be made from Table 4 when we compare the tensile strength values of EPON 862-fiber glass composite before and after 5 weight percent B₄C nanoparticulate addition. The reason for the lowering of load bearing capability of the composite could be improper infiltration of the resin during processing of the composite via heated vacuum assisted resin transfer molding, leading to non-uniform distribution of B₄C. And the improper infiltration of the resin in presence of 5 weight percent B₄C nanoparticulates could probably be due to the catalytic effect that B₄C nanoparticulates could have on the curing process.

Dynamic mechanical analyzer was also used to study the effect of B₄C nanoparticulates addition on the damping behavior of EPON 862 resin and EPON 862 - fiber glass composite. Figure 6 shows the variation in energy dissipation or damping in terms of Tan δ as a function of temperature for EPON 862 resin and EPON 862 - fiber glass composite with and without B₄C nanoparticulates. With the introduction of 5 weight percent B₄C nanoparticulates in EPON 862 resin, there is a drastic improvement in the damping behavior. However, in EPON 862 - fiber glass composites, the corresponding increase is very small. Hybrid EPON 862 - fiber glass composite containing 5 weight percent B₄C nanoparticulates could be expected to exhibit slightly higher impact strength than the two-phase EPON 862 - fiber glass composite. Tan δ curves are also indicators of homogeneity of epoxy network [15]. Peak factor, which is the measure of full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Tan δ curves is normally used to get an idea about the homogeneity of epoxy network. In the current study, from Figure 6, it appears that peak factor in EPON 862 - fiber glass composite remains almost unchanged with the addition of 5 wt. % B₄C nanoparticulates. However, in case of neat EPON 862, addition of 5 wt. % B₄C nanoparticulates brings about dramatic change in the FWHM. Narrow Tan δ curve for EPON 862 resin in presence of 5 wt. % B₄C nanoparticulates would mean higher cross link density and greater homogeneity of epoxy network.

4 Concluding Remarks

EPON 862 - fiberglass hybrid composite was processed via heated vacuum assisted resin transfer molding. Presence of the B₄C in EPON 862 resin was not found to expedite the curing process. While the use of 5 weight percent B₄C tends to lower the tensile strength, and strain to failure of EPON 862 - fiberglass hybrid composite, it has little or no effect on elastic modulus of the composite. On the contrary, addition of 5 wt. % B₄C has a favorable effect on the dynamic mechanical properties of the matrix and the resulting hybrid composite. Even though incorporation of 5 wt. % B₄C brings about marginal degradation of tensile mechanical properties of the resulting composites, by the virtue of the ability of EPON 862 matrix to weather strong radiation doses and because of the higher thermal neutron cross section of B₄C, EPON 862 - fiberglass hybrid composite offers potential to integrate radiation shield material into the structural components of the spacecraft.

Materials	Number of Hydrogen Atoms per 1 cm ³ (x 10 ²²)
H ₂ (Liquid)	4.6
H ₂ (Solid)	5.2
Water	6.7
LiH	5.9
ZrH ₂	7.3
HfH ₂	7.6
AlH ₃	8.9
TiH ₂	9.1
VH ₂	10.5
TiH ₃	13.2
TiH _{3.8}	16.5
Polyethylene	7.9
Polystyrene	4.7
Polyimide	2.2
Polyamide	3.0
Cured Epoxy	5.1

Table 1. Density of Hydrogen in Different Materials [2 – 4]

Heating Rate Deg./Min.	Onset Temp °C	Peak Temp °C	E _a , Activation Energy, kJ mole ⁻¹
10	124.2	194.3	49.5
20	145	218.5	
25	158.5	232	
30	163.3	237.5	
40	168.6	245.1	

Table 2. Kinetic Parameters for Curing of EPON 862 Epicure Hardener Mixtures

Heating Rate Deg./Min.	Onset Temp °C	Peak Temp °C	E _a , Activation Energy, kJ mole ⁻¹
10	124.6	194.2	46.8
20	142.7	218.5	
30	164.8	238.7	
40	167.1	250.3	
50	184.5	261.4	

Table 3. Kinetic Parameters for Curing of EPON 862 Epicure Hardener Mixture with 5% Boron Carbide Nanoparticulates

		Epoxy-Fiber Composite	Hybrid Epoxy-Fiber-B ₄ C Composite
Tensile Strength (MPa)	Mean	161.7	110.2
	SD	18.4	16.0
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Mean	17.9	18.7
	SD	1.2	0.87
Strain to Failure (%)	Mean	1.93	1.16
	SD	0.05	0.25

Table 4. Tensile Properties of the Two Composites

Fig. 1. DSC Curves for EPON 862 – Epicure

Fig. 2. DSC Curves for EPON 862-Epicure-5% B₄C

Fig 3. Fractograph of EPON 862 – Fiber Composite

Fig. 4. Fractograph of EPON 862-Fiber Glass-B₄C Hybrid Composite

Fig. 5. DMA: Variation of Storage Modulus as a Function of Temperature

Fig. 6. DMA – Variation of Tan δ as a Function of Temperature

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